

SUMSETS WITH A MINIMUM NUMBER OF DISTINCT TERMS

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*Received: 5/7/24, Accepted: 2/1/25, Published: 2/21/25***Abstract**

For a set A of k elements from an additive abelian group G and a positive integer $r \leq k$, we consider the set of elements of G that can be written as a sum of h elements of A with at least r distinct elements. We denote this set by $h^{(\geq r)}A$. The set $h^{(\geq r)}A$ generalizes the classical sumsets hA and $\hat{h}A$ for $r = 1$ and $r = h$, respectively. As the main result of this article, we give an upper bound for the minimum size of $h^{(\geq r)}A$ over \mathbb{Z}_m for $m \geq 2$. Further, by an observation relating the sumsets hA , $\hat{h}A$, and $h^{(\geq r)}A$ we obtain the sharp lower bound on the size of $h^{(\geq r)}A$ and also characterize the set A for which the lower bound on the size of $h^{(\geq r)}A$ is tight over the groups \mathbb{Z} and \mathbb{Z}_p , where p is a prime number.

1. Introduction

In this article, p stands for a prime number, θ for the golden ratio $\frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2}$, G for an additive abelian group, \mathbb{Z} for the group of integers, and \mathbb{Z}_m for the group $\{0, 1, \dots, m-1\}$, where m is a positive integer. For a given set A of integers, $|A|$ denotes the number of elements of A .

For a non-empty subset A of G and a positive integer h , let hA denote the set of elements of G that can be written as a sum of h elements of A , and $\hat{h}A$ denote the set of elements of G that can be written as a sum of h distinct elements of A . The sets hA and $\hat{h}A$ are called sumsets and restricted sumsets, respectively. One of the important problems in additive combinatorics is to estimate the sumsets hA and $\hat{h}A$ in terms of the size of A and the integer h . Such problems are known as direct problems. Some of the early results in this direction are the Cauchy-Davenport theorem [6, 7, 8] and the Erdős-Heilbronn conjecture (or Dias da Silva-Hamidoune theorem) [9].

Theorem 1 (Cauchy-Davenport theorem [6, 7, 8]). *Let A be a non-empty k -element set in \mathbb{Z}_p . Then, for any positive integer h , we have*

$$|hA| \geq \min\{p, hk - h + 1\}.$$

Theorem 2 (Dias da Silva-Hamidoune theorem [9]). *Let A be a non-empty k -element set in \mathbb{Z}_p . Then, for any positive integer $h \leq k$, we have*

$$|hA| \geq \min\{p, hk - h^2 + 1\}.$$

Another important problem in additive number theory is determining the structure of a set A given some information on the size of the sumsets. These are classified as inverse problems. Examples of such results are Vosper’s theorem [21, 22], Nathanson’s theorem [17], and Freiman’s $3k - 4$ theorem [12].

Theorem 3 (Vosper’s theorem [21, 22]). *Let A be a non-empty k -element set in \mathbb{Z}_p with $k \geq 2$. If $h \geq 2$ and $|hA| = hk - h + 1 \leq p - 2$, then A is an arithmetic progression.*

Theorem 4 (Nathanson [17]). *Let A be a non-empty k -element set of integers with $k \geq 5$. If $2 \leq h \leq k - 2$ and $|hA| = hk - h^2 + 1$, then A is an arithmetic progression.*

Theorem 5 (Freiman’s $3k - 4$ theorem [12]). *Let $k \geq 3$. Let $A = \{a_0, a_1, \dots, a_{k-1}\}$ be a set of integers such that $0 = a_0 < a_1 < \dots < a_{k-1}$ and $d(A) = 1$. If $|2A| = 2k - 1 + b \leq 3k - 4$, then A is a subset of an arithmetic progression of length at most $k + b$.*

For recent results along this line, see [4, 5, 15, 16, 23].

In this paper, we consider a sumset that generalizes the sumsets hA and hA and also discuss the direct and inverse problems.

Definition 1. Let $A = \{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k\}$ be a non-empty finite set in G . Let $r \leq k$ be a positive integer. For integers $h \geq r$, we define

$$h^{(\geq r)}A := \left\{ \sum_{i \in I} x_i a_i : I \subset [1, k], |I| \geq r, x_i \geq 1 \text{ for all } i \in I, \text{ and } \sum_{i \in I} x_i = h \right\}.$$

Then $h^{(\geq r)}A = hA$ if $r = 1$ and $h^{(\geq r)}A = hA$ if $r = h$.

Before we state our main result, we present some background on the problem.

In 2006, Plagne [19] (also see [10, 20]) extended the Cauchy-Davenport theorem to the group \mathbb{Z}_m by finding the exact value of

$$\mu(\mathbb{Z}_m, k, h) = \min\{|hA| : A \subset \mathbb{Z}_m, |A| = k\}.$$

Theorem 6 (Plagne [19]). *Let m, k, h be positive integers with $k \leq m$. Then*

$$\mu(\mathbb{Z}_m, k, h) = \min\{(h \lceil k/d \rceil - h + 1)d : d \in D(m)\},$$

where $D(m)$ is the set of positive divisors of m .

Later, in 2016, Bajnok [3] considered the analogous function $\hat{\mu}(\mathbb{Z}_m, k, h) = \min\{|\hat{h}A| : A \subset \mathbb{Z}_m, |A| = k\}$ and proved an upper bound for $\hat{\mu}(\mathbb{Z}_m, k, h)$ by estimating the exact size of the set $\hat{h}A_d(m, k)$, where $\hat{h}A_d(m, k)$ is defined in the following way. For a fixed positive divisor d of m , consider the subgroup $H = \{0, m/d, \dots, (d-1)(m/d)\}$ of \mathbb{Z}_m of order d . Write $k = ud + v$ for some non-negative integers u, v with $1 \leq v \leq d$. Define

$$A_d(m, k) := \bigcup_{i=0}^{u-1} \left\{ i + H \right\} \cup \left\{ u + j \cdot \frac{m}{d} : j = 0, 1, \dots, v-1 \right\}. \tag{1}$$

The following is the theorem of Bajnok.

Theorem 7 (Bajnok [3]). *Let h, k , and m be positive integers such that $k \leq m$. Let d be a positive divisor of m . Let $A_d(m, k)$ be the set of k elements defined in (1). If $h = k$, then $|\hat{h}A_d(m, k)| = 1$, and if $h > k$, then $|\hat{h}A_d(m, k)| = 0$. For $1 \leq h \leq k-1$, let v and w be the positive remainders of k and h modulo d , respectively. Then*

$$|\hat{h}A_d(m, k)| = \begin{cases} \min\{m, (h \lceil \frac{k}{d} \rceil - h + 1)d, hk - h^2 + 1\} & \text{if } h \leq \min\{v, d-1\}, \\ \min\{m, hk - h^2 + 1 - \delta_d\} & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

where

$$\delta_d = \begin{cases} (v-w)w - (d-1) & \text{if } w < v, \\ (d-w)(w-v) - (d-1) & \text{if } v < w < d, \\ d-1 & \text{if } v = w = d, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

The main result of this paper is the following theorem along the lines of Theorem 7.

Theorem 8. *Let m, k, r be positive integers such that $r \leq k \leq m$. For a fixed positive divisor d of m , let $A_d(m, k) \subset \mathbb{Z}_m$ be a set of k elements defined in (1). Let v, w be the respective positive remainders of k, r modulo d . Then, for every integer $h > r$, we have*

$$|h^{(\geq r)}A_d(m, k)| = \begin{cases} \min\{m, (h \lceil \frac{k}{d} \rceil - h + 1)d, h(k-1) - r(r-1) + 1\} & \text{if } r \leq \min\{v, d-1, k-1\} \\ \min\{m, h(k-1) - r(r-1) + 1 - \epsilon_d\} & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

where

$$\epsilon_d = \begin{cases} (h-r)(v-1) + w(v-w) - (d-1) & \text{if } w < v \\ (h-r)(v-1) + (d-w)(w-v) - (d-1) & \text{if } v < w < d \\ (h-r)(v-1) - (d-1) & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

If we set $\mu^{(\geq r)}(\mathbb{Z}_m, k, h) := \min\{|h^{(\geq r)}A| : A \subset \mathbb{Z}_m, |A| = k\}$, analogous to the functions $\mu(\mathbb{Z}_m, k, h)$ and $\tilde{\mu}(\mathbb{Z}_m, k, h)$, we obtain the following upper bound from Theorem 8:

$$\mu^{(\geq r)}(\mathbb{Z}_m, k, h) \leq \min\{|h^{(\geq r)}A_d(m, k)| : d \in D(m)\}. \tag{2}$$

2. Proof of Main Result

In this section we prove Theorem 8, for which we require the following lemma.

Lemma 1 (Bajnok [3]). *Let d and t be positive integers with $t \leq d - 1$, and let $\ell \in \mathbb{Z}_d$. Then there is a t -element set $L = \{\ell_1, \dots, \ell_t\}$ in \mathbb{Z}_d for which $\ell_1 + \dots + \ell_t = \ell$.*

Proof of Theorem 8. For a fixed positive divisor d of m , consider the subgroup $H = \{0, m/d, \dots, (d - 1)(m/d)\}$ of order d . Let $k = ud + v$ with $1 \leq v \leq d$, and

$$A_d(m, k) = \bigcup_{j=0}^{u-1} \left\{ j + H \right\} \cup \left\{ u + \ell \cdot \frac{m}{d} : \ell = 0, 1, \dots, v - 1 \right\}.$$

Since w is the positive remainder of r modulo d , we have $r = qd + w$ with some non-negative integer q . By definition every element of $h^{(\geq r)}A_d(m, k)$ is of the form

$$(j_1 + \dots + j_h) + (\ell_1 + \dots + \ell_h) \cdot \frac{m}{d}, \tag{3}$$

where $j_1, \dots, j_h \in \{0, 1, \dots, u\}$ and $\ell_1, \dots, \ell_h \in \{0, 1, \dots, d - 1\}$, with the following two added conditions:

- (i) when any of the j -indices equals u , the corresponding ℓ -index is at most $v - 1$,
- (ii) there are at least r distinct $j + \ell \cdot (m/d)$ in every sum of the form (3).

Let us denote the least value of $j_1 + \dots + j_h$ in (3) by j_{min} and the largest value of $j_1 + \dots + j_h$ in (3) by j_{max} . Then

$$j_{min} = (h - r + d) \cdot 0 + d \cdot 1 + d \cdot 2 + \dots + d \cdot (q - 1) + w \cdot q = q(r + w - d)/2.$$

On the other hand, to calculate j_{max} we consider the following four possible cases. If $q = 0$ and $w > v$, then $r = w > v$ and $1 \leq w - v \leq d - 1$. Therefore

$$j_{max} = (h - r + v) \cdot u + (w - v) \cdot (u - 1) = hu - r + v.$$

If $q = 0$ and $w \leq v$, then $r = w \leq v$. Therefore

$$j_{max} = h \cdot u = hu - r + w.$$

If $q \geq 1$ and $w > v$, then by writing $r = v + qd + (w - v)$, where $1 \leq w - v \leq d - 1$, we get

$$j_{max} = (h - r + v) \cdot u + d \cdot (u - 1) + \dots + d \cdot (u - q) + (w - v) \cdot (u - q - 1).$$

After simplification we get

$$j_{max} = hu - r + vq - \frac{q(r + w - d)}{2} + v.$$

Finally, if $q \geq 1$ and $w \leq v$, then by writing $r = v + (q - 1)d + (d + w - v)$, where $1 \leq d + w - v \leq d$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} j_{max} &= (h - r + v) \cdot u + d \cdot (u - 1) + \dots + d \cdot (u - q + 1) + (d + w - v) \cdot (u - q) \\ &= (h - r + v) \cdot u + d \cdot (u - 1) + \dots + d \cdot (u - q) + (w - v) \cdot (u - q - 1) + (w - v) \\ &= hu - r + vq - \frac{q(r + w - d)}{2} + w. \end{aligned}$$

We can combine the above four possible values of j_{max} and write in the following unified form

$$j_{max} = hu - r + vq - \frac{q(r + w - d)}{2} + \min\{v, w\}.$$

Since $j = j_1 + \dots + j_h$ can assume any integer value between j_{min} and j_{max} , the sumset $h^{(\geq r)}A_d(m, k)$ lies in exactly $\min\{m/d, j_{max} - j_{min} + 1\}$ cosets of H . Thus,

$$|h^{(\geq r)}A_d(m, k)| \leq \min\{m, (j_{max} - j_{min} + 1)d\}, \tag{4}$$

where after simplification we can write

$$(j_{max} - j_{min} + 1)d = h(k - 1) - r(r - 1) - (h - r)(v - 1) - w(v - w) + d \cdot \min\{0, v - w\} + d.$$

Equation (4) gives an upper bound for the size of $h^{(\geq r)}A_d(m, k)$. However, to compute the exact value of $|h^{(\geq r)}A_d(m, k)|$ we need to consider the following three cases.

Case 1: $r = k$. In this case $u = q$ and $v = w$. Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} |h^{(\geq r)}A_d(m, k)| &= \min\{m, (j_{max} - j_{min} + 1)d\} \\ &= \min\{m, h(k - 1) - r(r - 1) - (h - r)(v - 1) - w(v - w) + d \cdot \min\{0, v - w\} \\ &\hspace{15em} + d\} \\ &= \min\{m, h(k - 1) - r(r - 1) - (h - r)(v - 1) + d\}. \end{aligned}$$

Case 2: $r = 1$. In this case $h^{(\geq r)}A_d(m, k)$ is simply $hA_d(m, k)$. So,

$$h^{(\geq r)}A_d(m, k) = \bigcup_{j=0}^{hu-1} \left\{ j + H \right\} \cup \left\{ hu + \ell \cdot \frac{m}{d} : \ell = 0, 1, \dots, h(v-1) \right\}.$$

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} |h^{(\geq r)}A_d(m, k)| &= \min\{m, hud + \min\{d, hv - h + 1\}\} \\ &= \min\{m, (hu + 1)d, h(ud + v) - h + 1\} \\ &= \min\{m, (h\lceil k/d \rceil - h + 1)d, h(k - 1) + 1\} \\ &= \min\{m, (h\lceil k/d \rceil - h + 1)d, h(k - 1) - r(r - 1) + 1\}. \end{aligned}$$

Case 3: $2 \leq r \leq k - 1$. We divide the proof of this case into the following six possible subcases.

Subcase 1: Assume that $r \leq v$ and $r < d$. Then $q = 0$, $r = w < d$, and $r = w \leq v$. Therefore, $j_{min} = 0$ and $j_{max} = hu$. Thus, by Lemma 1, we get

$$h^{(\geq r)}A_d(m, k) = \bigcup_{j=0}^{hu-1} \left\{ j + H \right\} \cup \left\{ hu + \ell \cdot \frac{m}{d} : \ell = \frac{r(r-1)}{2}, \frac{r(r-1)}{2} + 1, \dots, h(v-1) - \frac{r(r-1)}{2} \right\}.$$

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} |h^{(\geq r)}A_d(m, k)| &= \min\{m, hud + \min\{d, h(v-1) - r(r-1) + 1\}\} \\ &= \min\{m, (hu + 1)d, hud + h(v-1) - r(r-1) + 1\} \\ &= \min\{m, (h\lceil k/d \rceil - h + 1)d, h(k-1) - r(r-1) + 1\}. \end{aligned}$$

Subcase 2: Assume that $r = v = d$. Then $q = 0$ and $w = r = d$. This implies $j_{min} = 0$ and $j_{max} = hu$. Further, since $r = d$, $k = ud + v = (u + 1)d$, and $r < k$, we have $u \geq 1$. Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} h^{(\geq r)}A_d(m, k) &= \left\{ \ell \cdot \frac{m}{d} : \ell = \frac{d(d-1)}{2}, \frac{d(d-1)}{2} + 1, \dots, h(d-1) - \frac{d(d-1)}{2} \right\} \bigcup_{j=1}^{hu-1} \left\{ j + H \right\} \\ &\quad \cup \left\{ hu + \ell \cdot \frac{m}{d} : \ell = \frac{d(d-1)}{2}, \frac{d(d-1)}{2} + 1, \dots, h(d-1) - \frac{d(d-1)}{2} \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} |h^{(\geq r)}A_d(m, k)| &= \min\{m, (hu - 1)d + 2 \cdot \min\{d, h(d-1) - d(d-1) + 1\}\} \\ &= \min\{m, (hu + 1)d, (hu - 1)d + 2(h - d)(d - 1) + 2\}. \end{aligned}$$

As $h \geq r + 1 = d + 1$ and $d \geq 1$, we have $(hu - 1)d + 2(h - d)(d - 1) + 2 \geq (hu + 1)d$. Therefore,

$$|h^{(\geq r)} A_d(m, k)| = \min\{m, (hu + 1)d\} = \min\{m, (h\lceil k/d \rceil - h + 1)d\}.$$

But, $(h\lceil k/d \rceil - h + 1)d = h(k - 1) - r(r - 1) - (h - r)(v - 1) + d$, thus, we get

$$|h^{(\geq r)} A_d(m, k)| = \min\{m, h(k - 1) - r(r - 1) - (h - r)(v - 1) + d\}.$$

Subcase 3: Assume that $r > v$, $w \neq d$, and $w \neq v$. Then, by Lemma 1, we have

$$h^{(\geq r)} A_d(m, k) = \bigcup_{j=j_{\min}}^{j_{\max}} \{j + H\}.$$

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} |h^{(\geq r)} A_d(m, k)| &= \min\{m, (j_{\max} - j_{\min} + 1)d\} \\ &= \min\{m, h(k - 1) - r(r - 1) - (h - r)(v - 1) - w(v - w) + d \cdot \min\{0, v - w\} + d\}. \end{aligned}$$

Subcase 4: Assume that $r > v$, $w = d$, and $w \neq v$. Then $r = (q + 1)d$ and $k = ud + v$ with $v < d$. This implies $j_{\min} = \frac{q(q+1)d}{2}$ and $j_{\max} = hu$. Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} h^{(\geq r)} A_d(m, k) &= \left\{ \frac{q(q + 1)d}{2} + \ell \cdot \frac{m}{d} : \ell = \frac{(q + 1)d(d - 1)}{2}, \frac{(q + 1)d(d - 1)}{2} + 1, \dots, \right. \\ &\quad \left. \frac{(q + 1)d(d - 1)}{2} + (h - r)(d - 1) \right\} \bigcup_{j=\frac{q(q+1)d}{2}+1}^{hu} \{j + H\}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} |h^{(\geq r)} A_d(m, k)| &= \min\{m, \min\{d, (h - r)(d - 1) + 1\} + (j_{\max} - j_{\min})d\} \\ &= \min\{m, (j_{\max} - j_{\min} + 1)d, (j_{\max} - j_{\min})d + (h - r)(d - 1) + 1\} \\ &= \min\{m, h(k - 1) - r(r - 1) - (h - r)(v - 1) + d, h(k - 1) - r(r - 1) - (h - r)(v - d) + 1\}. \end{aligned}$$

Note that

$$h(k - 1) - r(r - 1) - (h - r)(v - 1) + d \leq h(k - 1) - r(r - 1) - (h - r)(v - d) + 1$$

if and only if

$$(h - r)(d - 1) \geq d - 1.$$

As $h > r$, the latter inequality is true. Hence,

$$|h^{(\geq r)} A_d(m, k)| = \min\{m, h(k - 1) - r(r - 1) - (h - r)(v - 1) + d\}.$$

Subcase 5: Assume that $r > v$, $w \neq d$, and $w = v$. Then $r = qd + v$ and $k = ud + v$ with $v = w < d$. This implies $j_{\min} = q(r + w - d)/2$ and $j_{\max} = hu - r + v - \frac{q(r - v - d)}{2}$. Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} & h^{(\geq r)} A_d(m, k) \\ &= \bigcup_{j=j_{\min}}^{j_{\max}-1} \left\{ j + H \right\} \cup \left\{ j_{\max} + \ell \cdot \frac{m}{d} : \ell = \frac{d(d-1)q}{2} + \frac{v(v-1)}{2}, \right. \\ & \quad \left. \frac{d(d-1)q}{2} + \frac{v(v-1)}{2} + 1, \dots, \frac{d(d-1)q}{2} + \frac{v(v-1)}{2} + (h-r)(d-1) \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} & |h^{(\geq r)} A_d(m, k)| \\ &= \min\{m, (j_{\max} - j_{\min})d + \min\{d, (h - r)(d - 1) + 1\}\} \\ &= \min\{m, (j_{\max} - j_{\min} + 1)d, (j_{\max} - j_{\min})d + (h - r)(d - 1) + 1\} \\ &= \min\{m, (j_{\max} - j_{\min} + 1)d\} \\ &= \min\{m, h(k - 1) - r(r - 1) - (h - r)(v - 1) + d\}. \end{aligned}$$

Subcase 6: Assume that $r > v$ and $w = v = d$. Then $r = (q + 1)d$ and $k = (u + 1)d$. Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} & h^{(\geq r)} A_d(m, k) \\ &= \left\{ j_{\min} + \ell \cdot \frac{m}{d} : \ell = \frac{(q+1)d(d-1)}{2}, \dots, \frac{(q+1)d(d-1)}{2} + (h-r)(d-1) \right\} \\ & \quad \bigcup_{j=j_{\min}+1}^{j_{\max}-1} \left\{ j + H \right\} \cup \left\{ j_{\max} + \ell \cdot \frac{m}{d} : \ell = \frac{(q+1)d(d-1)}{2}, \dots, \right. \\ & \quad \left. \frac{(q+1)d(d-1)}{2} + (h-r)(d-1) \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |h^{(\geq r)}A_d(m, k)| \\
 &= \min\{m, (j_{\max} - j_{\min} - 1)d + 2 \cdot \min\{d, (h - r)(d - 1) + 1\}\} \\
 &= \min\{m, (j_{\max} - j_{\min} + 1)d, (j_{\max} - j_{\min} - 1)d + 2(h - r)(d - 1) + 2\} \\
 &= \min\{m, h(k - 1) - r(r - 1) - (h - r)(v - 1) + d, h(k - 1) - r(r - 1) \\
 &\qquad\qquad\qquad + (h - r - 1)(d - 1) + 1\} \\
 &= \min\{m, h(k - 1) - r(r - 1) - (h - r)(v - 1) + d\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

□

3. An Observation and its Consequences

Recall that in the introduction we defined the sumsets hA and $\hat{h}A$ for positive integers h . Here we add the convention that $0A = \emptyset A = \{0\}$. As every element of $h^{(\geq r)}A$ is a sum of h terms of A with at least r of them distinct, we have the following lemma.

Lemma 2. *Let A be a non-empty k -element set in G . Let r be a positive integer such that $r \leq k$. Then, for every positive integer $h \geq r$, we have*

$$h^{(\geq r)}A = (h - r)A + r\hat{A}. \tag{5}$$

We note that this lemma does not provide a simple proof of Theorem 8. However, we can use it to obtain some direct and inverse results for $h^{(\geq r)}A$ (see Theorems 9, 11, and 12). We can also use Lemma 2 to obtain a Freiman’s $3k - 4$ theorem-type result for $h^{(\geq r)}A$. We start with the following direct theorem.

Theorem 9. *Let k, r be positive integers with $r \leq k$. Then, for every positive integer $h \geq r$ and non-empty k -element set A in \mathbb{Z}_p , we have*

$$|h^{(\geq r)}A| \geq \min\{p, h(k - 1) - r(r - 1) + 1\}. \tag{6}$$

This lower bound is sharp.

To prove this theorem we shall use Theorem 1 together with the following theorem, which is another version of the Cauchy-Davenport theorem.

Theorem 10 ([18]). *Let A, B be non-empty subsets of \mathbb{Z}_p , where p is a prime number. Then*

$$|A + B| \geq \min\{p, |A| + |B| - 1\}.$$

Proof of Theorem 9. The case $k = 1$ is obvious. Assume that $k \geq 2$. By Lemma 2, we have $h^{(\geq r)}A = (h - r)A + r\hat{A}$. Then, by Theorem 10,

$$|h^{(\geq r)}A| = |(h - r)A + r\hat{A}| \geq \min\{p, |(h - r)A| + |r\hat{A}| - 1\}.$$

Now, by applying Theorem 1 on $(h - r)A$ and Theorem 2 on $r\hat{A}$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} |h^{(\geq r)}A| &\geq \min\{p, |(h - r)A| + |r\hat{A}| - 1\} \\ &\geq \min\{p, \min\{p, (h - r)(k - 1) + 1\} + \min\{p, r(k - r) + 1\} - 1\} \\ &\geq \min\{p, (h - r)(k - 1) + r(k - r) + 1\} \\ &= \min\{p, h(k - 1) - r(r - 1) + 1\}. \end{aligned}$$

This establishes the lower bound in Equation (6).

Choose a prime number p and positive integers h, r, k such that $r \leq \min\{h, k\}$ and $h(k - 1) - r(r - 1) + 1 \leq p$. Let $A = [1, k] \subset \mathbb{Z}_p$. Then

$$h^{(\geq r)}A \subset [(h - r + 1) \cdot 1 + 2 + 3 + \dots + r, (h - r + 1) \cdot k + (k - 1) + (k - 2) + \dots + (k - r + 1)].$$

Therefore,

$$|h^{(\geq r)}A| \leq h(k - 1) - r(r - 1) + 1.$$

This upper bound together with Equation (6) shows that $|h^{(\geq r)}A| = h(k - 1) - r(r - 1) + 1$. Hence, the lower bound in Equation (6) is sharp. \square

The following theorem gives the structure of set A for which the bound in Theorem 9 is tight.

Theorem 11. *Let k, r be positive integers with $k \geq 2$ and $r \leq k$. Let $h \geq r + 2$ be a positive integer and A be a non-empty k -element set in \mathbb{Z}_p with*

$$|h^{(\geq r)}A| = h(k - 1) - r(r - 1) + 1 \leq p - 2.$$

Then A is an arithmetic progression.

Proof. As any set of two elements is an arithmetic progression, we shall assume that $k \geq 3$. Observe that

$$\begin{aligned} \max\{(h - r)(k - 1) + 1, r(k - r) + 1\} &\leq (h - r)(k - 1) + r(k - r) + 1 \\ &= h(k - 1) - r(r - 1) + 1 \\ &\leq p - 2. \end{aligned}$$

As it is given that

$$|h^{(\geq r)}A| = h(k - 1) - r(r - 1) + 1,$$

from the proof of Theorem 9, we obtain

$$|(h - r)A| = \min\{p, (h - r)(k - 1) + 1\} = (h - r)(k - 1) + 1 \leq p - 2.$$

Then, Theorem 3 implies that the set A is an arithmetic progression. \square

One can prove the following theorem using similar arguments as in Theorem 9 and Theorem 11.

Theorem 12. *Let k, r be positive integers with $r \leq k$. Then for every positive integer $h \geq \max\{r, 2\}$ and non-empty k -element set A of integers, we have*

$$|h^{(\geq r)}A| \geq h(k-1) - r(r-1) + 1. \tag{7}$$

Furthermore, if $|h^{(\geq r)}A| = h(k-1) - r(r-1) + 1$ and

1. $k \geq 2$ in case $h \geq r + 2$,
2. $k \geq 5$ and $2 \leq r \leq k - 2$ in case $h = r$ or $h = r + 1$,

then A is an arithmetic progression.

From Theorem 12 it follows that the set A is an arithmetic progression if the lower bound for $|h^{(\geq r)}A|$ is tight. A natural question that arises here is: up to what deviation from the lower bound in Theorem 12 can one cover the set A inside a “small” arithmetic progression? To answer such a question, one possible way is to express the size of $h^{(\geq r)}A$ in terms of the size of $(h-1)^{(\geq r)}A$ or lower order sumsets. Theorem 14 is one such result in this direction, which directly follows from Lemma 2 and the following theorem of Lev [13].

Theorem 13 (Lev [13]). *Let $k \geq 3$. Let $A = \{a_0, a_1, \dots, a_{k-1}\}$ be a set of integers such that $0 = a_0 < a_1 < \dots < a_{k-1}$ and $\gcd(A) = 1$. Then, for $h \geq 2$, we have*

$$|hA| \geq |(h-1)A| + \min\{a_{k-1}, h(k-2) + 1\}.$$

Theorem 14. *Let r, k be positive integers such that $k \geq 3$ and $r \leq k$. Let $A = \{a_0, a_1, \dots, a_{k-1}\}$ be a set of k integers such that $0 = a_0 < a_1 < \dots < a_{k-1}$ and $\gcd(A) = 1$. Then, for $h \geq r + 2$, we have*

$$|h^{(\geq r)}A| \geq |rA| + |(h-r-1)A| + \min\{a_{k-1}, (h-r)(k-2) + 1\}.$$

4. Further Remarks

Another sumset that may come immediately to the reader’s mind is the sumset $h^{(\leq r)}A$, which contains those elements of the group G that are the sum of h elements of A with at most r distinct elements. The sumset hA is a special case of $h^{(\leq r)}A$ for $r = h$.

Let $A = \{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k\}$ be a set of k integers. Then for any positive integer h the sumset hA contains at least the following $hk - h + 1$ elements written in an

increasing order:

$$\begin{aligned} ha_1 &< (h-1)a_1 + a_2 < \cdots < a_1 + (h-1)a_2 < \\ ha_2 &< (h-1)a_2 + a_3 < \cdots < a_2 + (h-1)a_3 < \\ &\vdots \\ ha_{k-1} &< (h-1)a_{k-1} + a_k < \cdots < a_{k-1} + (h-1)a_k < \\ &ha_k. \end{aligned}$$

Observe that to get the minimum number of elements (which is $hk - h + 1$) in the sumset $hA = h^{(\leq h)}A$, we only required elements in hA which are sums of at most two distinct elements of A (see the list of elements above). Thus, the sumset $h^{(\leq r)}A$ contains at least $hk - h + 1$ distinct elements for all $r \geq 2$. Therefore, we ask the following question for integers $r \geq 2$.

Question 1. Is it always the case that the minimum size of both the sumsets hA and $h^{(\leq r)}A$ are the same in any abelian group G , where the minimum runs over the subsets of G of size (say) k ?

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